

A new way to find height of tringle

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Abstract:

This paper introduces a new formula for calculating the height of a triangle, a fundamental geometric parameter, which has significant implications in various scientific and engineering disciplines. Traditional methods for determining the height of a triangle rely on well-established formulas derived from Heron's formula, the Pythagorean theorem, and trigonometric identities. However, these methods often require extensive computational effort or specific conditions, such as knowing the lengths of all sides.

This research aims to simplify the process of height determination by proposing a novel approach that reduces computational complexity while maintaining accuracy. The new formula is derived through an innovative combination of geometric principles and algebraic manipulations. Specifically, we explore the relationships between the triangle's base, area, and certain key ratios that simplify the height calculation.

The implications of this discovery are far-reaching, offering potential applications in fields such as computer graphics, architectural design, and robotics, where efficient geometric computations are crucial. Additionally, this formula enhances educational methodologies in geometry by providing an alternative, more accessible approach to understanding triangle properties.

Keywords: Triangle Height, Geometric Formula, Computational Geometry, Mathematical Proof, Algebraic Manipulation, Educational Tool, Computational Efficiency.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background:

Using traditional Brahmagupta's formula gives the area K of a cyclic quadrilateral whose sides have lengths a, b, c, d as

$$K = \sqrt{(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)(s-d)}$$

where s , the semi perimeter, is defined to be

$$s = \frac{a+b+c+d}{2}.$$

Fig1: Cyclic quadrilateral

$$K = \sqrt{(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)(s-d)}$$

This formula generalizes Heron's formula for the area of a triangle, like this:

If $d=0$ then, the area of a triangle

$$A = \sqrt{s(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)}.$$

After finding the area of tringle we need to calculate height like this:

$$h = \frac{(A*2)}{c} \quad c \text{ is base.}$$

1.2 Objectives

Main objective of this paper to find height of any tringle in proper way, without calculating area. A direct formula is given here which can calculate more easily.

Proposed formula of calculating height of any tringle is:

$$f(a, b, c) = \sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

c is base side of tringle.

2.Methodology:

Fig2: Finding height

Let we have a triangle ABC and side AB, BC and CA, assume that the length of all side are different which are a, b and c unit. The height of triangle h, assuming BC be ground side. Now finding height using three side a, b and c.

Height of triangle,

$$f(a, b, c) = \sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

1.1 Prove of equation:

Let, we assumed that

$$m + n = c$$

$$h^2 + m^2 = a^2$$

$$h^2 + n^2 = b^2$$

Therefore,

$$h^2 + m^2 = a^2$$

$$\text{Or, } m^2 = a^2 - h^2$$

$$\text{Or, } m = \pm\sqrt{a^2 - h^2} \quad \dots (i)$$

And

$$h^2 + n^2 = b^2$$

$$\text{Or, } n^2 = b^2 - h^2$$

$$\text{Or, } n = \pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2} \quad \dots (ii)$$

So, adding (i) and (ii)

$$m + n = \pm\sqrt{a^2 - h^2} + [\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}]$$

$$\text{Or, } c = \pm\sqrt{a^2 - h^2} + [\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}]$$

$$\text{Or, } \sqrt{a^2 - h^2} = c - [\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}]$$

$$\text{Or, } a^2 - h^2 = c^2 - 2c[\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}] + b^2 - h^2$$

$$\text{Or, } a^2 = c^2 - 2c[\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}] + b^2$$

$$\text{Or, } 2c[\pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2}] = b^2 + c^2 - a^2$$

$$\text{Or, } \pm\sqrt{b^2 - h^2} = -\left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)$$

$$\text{Or, } b^2 - h^2 = \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2$$

$$\text{Or, } h^2 = b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2$$

$$\text{Or, } h = \pm\sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

So, there for height of any triangle,

$$h = \sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

Where:

- a, b and c length of three side of triangle
- maintain serial
- c is ground side.

1.2 A modified version of this equation:

It can write that equation two way like this

$$1. \quad h^2 = b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2$$

$$2. \quad h^2 = a^2 - \left(\frac{b^2 - a^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2$$

adding equation 1 and 2

$$\begin{aligned} 2h^2 &= (a^2 + b^2) - \frac{(a^2 - b^2 - c^2)^2 + (a^2 - b^2 + c^2)^2}{4c^2} \\ &= (a^2 + b^2) - \frac{2(a^2 - b^2)^2 + 2(c^2)^2}{4c^2} \\ &= (a^2 + b^2) - \frac{(a^2 - b^2)^2 + c^4}{2c^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Or, } h^2 &= \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{2} - \frac{(a^2 - b^2)^2 + c^4}{4c^2} \\ &= \frac{2(a^2 + b^2)c^2 - (a^2 - b^2)^2 + c^4}{4c^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Or, } h = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{(a^2 + b^2) - \frac{(a^2 - b^2)^2 + c^4}{2c^2}}$$

So, this the modified version of equation.

More simplification of this equation for avoiding large calculation:

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2(a^2 + b^2) - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2}{c}\right)^2 - c^2}$$

3. Finding area of triangle:

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot c \cdot h = \frac{1}{2} \cdot c \cdot \sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(bc)^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2}\right)^2}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{(2bc)^2 - (a^2 - b^2 - c^2)^2}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{-((a^2 - b^2 - c^2)^2 - (2bc)^2)}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{-(a^2 - b^2 - c^2 + 2bc)(a^2 - b^2 - c^2 - 2bc)}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{-(a^2 - (b^2 - 2bc + c^2))(a^2 - (b^2 + 2bc + c^2))}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{-(a^2 - (b - c)^2)(a^2 - (b + c)^2)}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \frac{1}{4} \sqrt{-(a + b - c)(a - b + c)(a + b + c)(a - b - c)}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \sqrt{-\frac{(a+b+c-2c)}{2} \cdot \frac{(a+b-2b+c)}{2} \cdot \frac{(a+b+c)}{2} \cdot \frac{(2a-a-b-c)}{2}}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \sqrt{\frac{(a+b+c-2c)}{2} \cdot \frac{(a+b+c-2b)}{2} \cdot \frac{(a+b+c)}{2} \cdot \frac{(a+b+c-2a)}{2}}$$

$$\text{Or, } A = \sqrt{\left(\frac{a+b+c}{2} - c\right) \left(\frac{a+b+c}{2} - b\right) \left(\frac{a+b+c}{2}\right) \left(\frac{a+b+c}{2} - a\right)}$$

$$\text{If } s = \frac{(a+b+c)}{2}$$

The equation will be,

$$A = \sqrt{s(s-a)(s-b)(s-c)}$$

This is equation of Heron's area finding formula of triangle.

So, area can find using any equation form solving step.

4. Proof of equation by comparing result:

Let we have triangle which have three side $a=3$, $b=5$, $c=4$, and ground line is c then height of triangle will be $h=3$.

Using Dip's formula for finding height of triangle,

$$h = \sqrt{5^2 - \left(\frac{3^2 - 5^2 - 4^2}{2 \cdot 4}\right)^2}$$

$$h = 3$$

5. Finding height of isosceles triangle:

Using Pythagoras theorem, we can find height of isosceles triangle,

$$h^2 = a^2 - \left(\frac{c}{2}\right)^2$$

$$h = \sqrt{a^2 - \left(\frac{c}{2}\right)^2}$$

Using dip's modified formula

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2(a^2 + a^2) - \left(\frac{a^2 - a^2}{c}\right)^2 - c^2}$$

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2(2a^2) - \left(\frac{0}{c}\right)^2 - c^2}$$

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{4a^2 - c^2}$$

$$h = \sqrt{\frac{4a^2}{4} - \frac{c^2}{4}}$$

$$h = \sqrt{a^2 - \left(\frac{c}{2}\right)^2} \text{ (proved)}$$

6. Extra case:

Finding height of triangle if opposite angle of base side (angle A) is 90 deg. (form Fig2)

$$a^2 + b^2 = m^2 + h^2 + n^2 + h^2$$

If angle A=90 deg, then,

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2$$

$$\text{So, } c^2 = m^2 + n^2 + 2h^2$$

$$\text{And } c = m + n$$

$$\text{Or, } (m + n)^2 = m^2 + n^2 + 2h^2$$

$$\text{Or, } 2h^2 = (m + n)^2 - m^2 - n^2$$

$$\text{Or, } 2h^2 = 2mn$$

$$\text{Or, } h = \sqrt{mn}, \text{ or } h = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

Conclusion:

- Now we can say that height of triangle,

$$h = \sqrt{b^2 - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2 - c^2}{2c}\right)^2}$$

a, b, c are side of triangle and c is base side of triangle.

- Some modified of this equation:

$$h = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{2(a^2 + b^2) - \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2}{c}\right)^2 - c^2}$$

- if opposite angle of base side is 90 deg (A=90 deg)

Reference:

1. Brahmagupta's formula [[Brahmagupta's formula - Wikipedia](#)]
2. Heron's formula [[Heron's formula - Wikipedia](#)]
3. Pythagorean theorem [[Pythagorean theorem - Wikipedia](#)]